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Entrepreneurship education for PhD students in engineering sciences

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ABSTRACT

In this article, we discuss the development of a specific entrepreneurship training programme and its integration into traditional doctoral education. We present a description and reflection on our new entrepreneurship training programme which is specifically designed for PhD students in engineering sciences. We propose a twofold approach: training programme development which takes into consideration, not only the initial skills level of participating students, but their future career perspectives as well. We define four skill development levels which are differentiated by specific requested learning outcomes. As a conclusion, we provide reflections on the future perspectives of entrepreneurship education in this specific context.

Conference Key Areas: Curriculum development, Engineering skills

Keywords: Doctoral education, Engineering science, Entrepreneurship training

INTRODUCTION

Doctoral students' education aims to develop highly specialised theoretical knowledge in students' research fields, as well as developing their skills and competencies in researching to help them better prepare their thesis [1]. These abilities are indispensable, not only to successfully complete their doctoral studies, but also for performing well in an academic career. However, only a minority of PhD students in engineering sciences will have the possibility to pursue an academic career in their research domain. According to the latest survey, the proportion of graduate engineering PhD students who started an academic career is in constant decline (from 52 % in 2010 to 43 % 2013) in France. The majority of them will make their career in industry and work in a business environment [2]. In this context, entrepreneurship education is viewed as a real facilitator in the transition of a constantly growing proportion of graduate PhD students from academic education to a work environment [3].

1 ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION

1.1 Entrepreneurship education for PhD students

Entrepreneurship education was introduced into the curriculum of French higher educational institutions relatively late, only over the past two decades. Its introduction was strongly encouraged and supported by the government in order to stimulate entrepreneurship activities and create employment [4]. However, the integration of entrepreneurship education in doctoral education programmes is still not generalised and depends mainly on institutional decisions. This is quite surprising despite the numerous benefits of these programmes for PhD students, industrial business organisations and higher educational institutions.

For PhD students, entrepreneurship education could appear as the cornerstone of their future employability: if they are to work in an industrial or business organisation, they have to possess not only well founded technical skills, but also business and entrepreneurship skills in order to allow them to operate successfully in this new environment. These 'non-technical' skills and competencies, often considered as secondary or complementary, have become vital for graduate doctoral students to acquire for when they start their career in industry. The possession of these transferable skills and competencies can give considerable advantages for them in the recruitment process.

For industrial organisations entrepreneurial skills and competencies have an important place in their skill requirements and are viewed as one of the key competencies nowadays. It is obvious that these skills and competencies are particularly important to build a solid entrepreneurial orientation which consists of innovativeness, proactiveness, risk taking, competitiveness and autonomy [5]. In a competence based market competition [6], employees' competencies are considered as one of their most valuable assets for them to be able to develop new and innovative products. The lack of these skills and competencies could considerably reduce their economic performance and their capacity to attain sustainable competitive advantages. This is even accentuated in industry where engineers' skills and competencies have a huge influence on the ability of organisations to create significant value added products and services.

From an academic perspective, the development of entrepreneurship education for engineering doctoral students has become an important issue. Several studies [7, 8, and 9] pointed out the positive effect of entrepreneurial education on the development of students' business skills and competencies, and also on their innovation capacity [10, 11]. Entrepreneurship education has numerous short-term effects, such as the raising of entrepreneurship awareness, elevating the understanding about enterprises, allowing for the development of an entrepreneurial mindset or an awareness concerning the attitudes and intention toward entrepreneurship etc. [12]. Furthermore, there are several widely recognised positive long-term effects of entrepreneurship education on society, such as developing an idea and patents generation, allowing for enterprise growth and increasing job creation which motivates the expansion of entrepreneurship education [13].

1.2 Doctoral entrepreneurship education programme in France

Despite its long-standing needs, entrepreneurship education is a relatively new phenomenon in PhD students' education in France. It was introduced into doctoral training only six years ago with the participation of a limited number of post-graduate engineering schools. With the support and encouragement of the government, it was launched by the CDEFI (Conference of Deans of French Schools of Engineering) in

the framework of a specific doctoral training programme after a two year experimental period (from 2011 to 2013) when the programme was tested by nine engineering higher educational institutions [14]. Since its introduction, the number of participating institutions has seen an exponential growth, as 26 engineering schools and 30 doctoral schools participate in this programme today [15]. This doctoral programme is open for all doctoral students, independent of their scientific disciplines, and it is not reserved solely for engineering doctoral students. However, on the national level, 50% of the participants are doctoral students in the domain of engineering sciences. This high participation of engineering doctoral students is mainly explained by the fact that engineering schools in France traditionally have a strong relationship with industry which gives them a good vision about what the industry needs and its requirements for skills and competencies.

The main objective of this programme is the development of the skill and competency requirements which doctoral students need in order to improve their employability which will allow them to work in a real business environment. As we mentioned before, the majority of PhD students in France pursue their career in an industrial business environment. However, contrary to other European countries (e.g. Germany, UK), PhD graduation is not really recognised by French industrial business organisations. In this context, this doctoral training has a specific purpose of making the recruitment of graduate PhD students more attractive in the labour market. According to a recent study [16], graduate PhD students have difficulty identifying accessible positions and the skill and competency requirements of industry outside of their research and development activities. This programme could help them to better understand the concept and practice of industrial business organisations, and not only better identify the required skills and competencies of the industry, but to take advantage of them.

1.3 Skills development

The definition of the required skills was based on the referential list 'DocPro' which was co-created between the national association of PhD students (Association Bernard Gregory), the CPU (Conference of University Presidents) and the MEDEF (French Business Confederation) and included 24 skills over four domains [17]. There is a well-defined correspondence table between the referential 'DocPro' and the skill definition of the doctoral entrepreneurship programme [14:15] to help students in the evaluation of their skills.

The required skills in the doctoral entrepreneurship training are divided into four principal categories with several components in each of them (Cf. Table 1). The first category is related to the engineering PhD students' ability to understand business concepts and practices. The second category is associated with project management and the capacity to work independently. The next category is composed of scientific and technical knowledge from the problem definition to the solution. The last category includes several social skills, such as interdisciplinary communication or language skills. For the obtainment of their certificate, students have to acquire at least 8 skills from these 15 skills by the end of the programme.

At the beginning of the training, as a part of the selection process, each engineering PhD student is asked to make a self-evaluation. Considered as the basis for the personalised programme construction, this self-evaluation is very important in defining what skills they need to develop. The result of this self-evaluation is very heterogeneous, as there is a huge difference in skill development in each discipline and even between the different fields of engineering science [18]. Furthermore, there

are large divergences at a personal level, as each engineering PhD student has his own personal academic and work experience.

Nevertheless, the selection of candidates is not based on students' initial skills, but essentially on their motivation and their capacity to integrate into a business work environment. Also, the engagement of candidates on this two year doctoral entrepreneurship education training is an important criterion of the selection process. Given the fact that this is highly personalised doctoral training, it requires an important investment from the institutions. For this reason, requiring a high level of students' engagement could limit abandonment and failure.

Fig. 1. Entrepreneurial skills development (Adapted from [14])

2 CURRICULUM DESIGN

In our engineering school, we have recently introduced a certified and adjusted two year entrepreneurship education programme. The curriculum development of the programme was based on the official recommendations of the CDEFI following the general framework of PhD programmes, which was designed to facilitate doctoral students' integration. This new entrepreneurship education programme is available for doctoral students who have successfully completed their first-year PhD studies and who have a proven record of engagement in their studies. We outline that students' engagement is particularly important in this programme for two main reasons: firstly, it is the longest doctoral programme proposed in our engineering school (lasting over two academic years) and secondly, it requires an important investment from our institution.

We have developed a highly personalised programme for our PhD students, which takes into account:

- Students' self-evaluation about their existing skills when they enter the programme and
- Their career prospects and the principal skills that they would need for their future professional activities.

As the participating PhD students are drawn from diverse engineering and scientific disciplines, they have very different skill sets when entering our entrepreneurship educational programme. Also, they have various career prospects depending on their personal preferences and opportunities. As we have a really heterogeneous participating population, we have applied a twofold approach (Cf. Figure 2) in the curriculum design, which simultaneously considers their initial skills level and their future working environment.

Fig. 2. Conceptual framework of the entrepreneurial programme development

2.1 Functional approach

We follow a functional approach in the curriculum design when participating students have a career desire to work in a business and industrial organisation. In this case, our main objective is the transmission of functional skills and knowledge to them. This approach is based on the development of general and specific business skills and depends on the participating student's skill development needs and requirements. Students have the choice of a large variety of modules which last a maximum of one semester and do not require long term engagement. We distinguish between two levels of skills development:

2.1.1. Entrepreneurship awareness raising

At the first level, we provide mainly theoretical knowledge and basic skills for raising their entrepreneurship awareness by giving them an insight into the life of businesses, in order for them to understand how it works. In this category, we have participating PhD students with a low level of initial skills on entering the programme. Typically, these participating students have a high level of scientific knowledge and skills, but have had a lack of opportunity to learn business subjects during their previous studies. For this reason, they generally need to acquire solid basic

knowledge and skills to be able to understand and to be ready to work in a business environment.

2.1.2. Specific entrepreneurship skills

At the second level, we take into account students' special interests and preferences and aim to develop entrepreneurship skills and competencies by focusing on what would be principally useful for their future professional careers. At this level, we have participating doctoral students who possess strong basic business skills and understanding. They are interested to be involved in specialised modules relevant to their particular, and often well-defined, objectives. Usually, they are enrolled in this programme to acquire expertise in specific subjects, in most cases related to their scientific and research activities, in order to enhance their potential career opportunities.

2.2 Practical approach

For participating PhD students who have the intention, in their short or long term career, to set up their own companies, we applied a practical approach in the curriculum development. The principal objective of this approach is the transmission of practical and behavioural competencies in order to teach them how to develop entrepreneurial activities. We provide a highly specialised and individualised entrepreneurship learning programme which includes the creation of a new business by doctoral students. In this case, participating students have to undertake the PBL based entrepreneurship modules which are longer than the modules of the functional approach and need two to four semesters of continuous work and engagement. It is manifest that this practical approach requires a clear long-term vision, strong engagement and perseverance from them. They have to be highly motivated to accomplish these modules in parallel to their research and scientific activities, especially in the final year of their PhD studies. In this approach, we differentiate two levels of skill development according to the objectives of their entrepreneurship project.

2.2.1. Entrepreneurial practice

At the basic level, they are required to develop an entrepreneurial project as a member of a multidisciplinary team composed of graduate and postgraduate students of other engineering and non-engineering domains. The main objective of this entrepreneurial project is to learn how to create their start-ups. Despite the fact that every year at the end of the module some of these projects are transformed into a real business, the vast majority of them are only created to achieve the learning outcomes. Participating PhD students generally have a long-term career goal to create their own companies. However, they would like to start their career as an employee in an industrial business organisation in order to gain initial real work experience.

2.2.2. Practical behavioural skills

At the advanced level, PhD students develop their own business based on their technological invention or pattern. The principal objective of this level is not only to learn to lay the foundations, but also to create their real ventures. This level requires a particularly high level of engagement from participating students. At the end of our two year training programme, these students have the possibility, after finishing their PhD studies, to enter our engineering school's incubator and continue their project. During their entrepreneurship programme, they receive regular tutorials from the facilitator of the incubator. Also, they have the opportunity to participate in the diverse activities organised by the incubator which can facilitate their integration to the incubator's community.

As it was presented in the last paragraphs, we have designed the curriculum of our entrepreneurship education programme based on four differentiated learning objectives. The implementation of this programme requires the cooperation between teachers in management domains, research laboratories, our school's incubator and our industrial partners. Teachers in management and researchers in engineering were particularly involved in the development of the functional skills. The transmission of behavioural skills and competencies was carried out essentially by the help of our incubator and industrial partners.

CONCLUSION

Providing engineering PhD students with a well-adapted and valuable entrepreneurship education, alongside with its incontestable and numerous benefits, remains an important challenge today. Given the fact that the vast majority of PhD students will progress to a career in industry, entrepreneurship training opportunities for post-graduate students in engineering sciences will be in a growing demand over the next decade. However, the integration of entrepreneurship training programmes within the framework of doctoral education is not really prevalent, and only a very low percentage of engineering PhD students could benefit from it today in France.

Our engineering school has decided to take the lead in developing a tailored entrepreneurship training programme to increase doctoral students' employability. The introduction of this programme was appreciated not only by doctoral students, but also by their research laboratories, incubators and industrial partners and it has developed a thriving cooperation between them. Our first experiences confirm, from the abundant number of candidates, doctoral students' awareness of the benefits and usefulness of this programme. However, despite the raising need from students, it is available only for a limited number of doctoral students. As a future perspective, it would be beneficial to make it available for each motivated PhD student.

We have adopted a double approach in our programme which was useful for participating PhD students to receive a better adjustment and personalisation of their learning objectives. Students have a choice between four different learning objectives in relation of their future perspectives. It would be interesting to explore the applied teaching methods in each category and investigate what the most adapted methods are. It could provide us with useful information in choosing the best methods and ameliorate our curriculum.

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